

Deliverable D 7.6 IP4MaaS leaflet, version 2

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable describes and shows the second version of the Project Leaflet developed by the IP4MaaS project. In this document we describe the objectives of the leaflet, as well as the structure and design.

This second leaflet, delivered at the end of the project, is the second out of two. A first leaflet was developed in the first stage of the project.

2 Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
CFM	Calls for Members
DL	Dissemination and exploitation leader
DoA	Description of the Action
EL	Ethical leader
EU	European Union
FS	Financial Statement
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
IP4	Innovation Programme 4
OC	Open Call
PC	Project coordinator
PM	Project manager
PMO	Project Management Office
PMT	Project Management Team
PO	Project Officer
QAC	Quality Assurance Committee
S2R JU	Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking
TL	Technical leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work package leader

3 Background

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D7.6 “Project Leaflet second version” in the in the framework of task 7.1 of the IP4MaaS project (S2R-OC-IP4-01-2020).

4 Objective/Aim

The objectives of the IP4MaaS communication and dissemination activities are to raise awareness and disseminate project developments and outcomes to key stakeholders, to ensure maximal exploitation of project results, to organise key project events, and finally to implement and update an appropriate online presence (website, social media).

The final leaflet of the IP4MaaS project an important tool to reach these goals. The leaflet has been developed to show in a concise, attractive way the outcomes of the IP4MaaS project, with a focus on the project demos.

By opting for a factsheet format, the IP4MaaS leaflet can be fully read in a relatively short amount of time, providing interested parties with all the outcomes in an instant.

The IP4MaaS leaflet can be found in Annex 2 of this document, and on the IP4MaaS website, via the link http://www.ip4maas.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/IP4MaaS_leaflet2.pdf.

5 Leaflet

5.1 Design of leaflet

The leaflet has been designed by an external agency, after a careful briefing by UITP on requirements and wishes. As explained in Chapter 4, it was decided to create a leaflet in ‘factsheet’ format, so only 2 pages. This has been done to provide facts and key points about IP4MaaS in a clear, concise, and easy-to-understand way.

The leaflet has been designed according to the IP4MaaS visual identity, which includes specific use of colour schemes and fonts. It was decided to keep the look and feel of the leaflet clean and modern, to reflect the innovative nature of the project.

5.2 Content of the leaflet

All key info on the IP4MaaS project and its outcomes is given on two pages. On page one, a short recap of the project is provided, including core info and objectives. After that, we dive deeper into the outcomes of the IP4MaaS demos: for each we describe their main objectives and their outcomes. Finally, more general conclusions are provided at the end.

6 Conclusions

By developing a project leaflet focused on results, the dissemination of project outcomes has been strengthened, what will advance the possible uptake of IP4MaaS solutions after project completion. When the project ended in June 2023, it was decided not to stop dissemination actions, but to actually strengthen them, seeing most project results were gathered only at the end of the project. Together with the UITP Project Brief, the Transferability Handbook, this leaflet forms one of the three main dissemination materials to show in a clear way what the IP4MaaS project has achieved.

7 Appendices

Annex I: IP4MaaS leaflet 2

IP4MaaS

The IP4MaaS project sought to advance the uptake of Mobility as a Service (MaaS) schemes in Europe, by analysing and testing existing technologies and assess them in terms of effectiveness, market acceptance, and user satisfaction.

Testing MaaS technologies to advance seamless multimodal mobility in Europe

Advancing IP4 technologies

Instead of developing new technologies, the IP4MaaS project tested solutions developed under the Innovation Programme 4 (IP4) of the Europe's Rail Joint Undertaking (previously Shift2Rail), an Initiative seeking to build a digital ecosystem for door-to-door travel with railways as its backbone.

The main aim of IP4MaaS was to act as a bridge between the needs and requirements of Transport Services Providers (TSPs) and travellers with the technologies developed within Europe's Rail to expand the functions of the IP4 digital ecosystem and in particular of the Travel Companion (the travel application developed within Shift2Rail allowing users to plan, book and execute their multimodal trips).

Budget
€2.5 million

Duration
31 months
(December 2020 – June 2023)

Coordinator
UITP (the International Association of Public Transport)

Consortium
26 European partners

Testing in six EU sites

IP4 technologies were demonstrated in six European sites: Padua, Liberec, Barcelona, Athens, Warsaw, Osijek. For each demo site, the main mobility pain points were identified and it was assessed how IP4 solutions could help to solve them.

Athens Greece

- Modes: metro, bus, taxis, bikes and walking
- Number of participants: 23 (phase 1), 36 (phase 2)

Enhancing multimodality by providing journey planning and integrated ticketing via a single app.

Results

- Users were enthusiastic about the attempts to develop a step towards MaaS in Athens.
- The assessment highlighted significant challenges, mainly related to technological and legal issues.
- Solutions drew attention to the need to address MaaS challenges for building a competing mobility service that is reliable, satisfies user needs and improves accessibility for all.

Padua Italy

- Modes: train, bus
- Number of participants: 13

Improving urban-surrounding connections and the efficiency of public transport services while reducing GHG emissions and unsustainable travel habits.

Results

- Users genuinely appreciated the application. The 'travellers' feedback' function was particularly appreciated.
- Training on how to use the app was considered important for properly realising its potential.
- Users would appreciate being able to find the app on widely-used app download platforms.

Liberec Czech Republic

- Modes: trams, buses, trains
- Number of participants: 124

In a mountainous area with scattered rural settlements, the demo wanted to achieve smoother travelling and improve the integration of all public transport modes.

Results

- Testers emphasised that the Travel Companion is user-friendly as it integrates all transport modes into a single travel solution and also supports eco-friendly transport solutions.
- Testers suggested a number of possible improvements to the app in order to further increase its user-friendliness and efficiency.

Osijek Croatia

- Modes: bus, trams, shared bike
- Number of participants: 41

Exploring the potential of creating a MaaS ecosystem in the Osijek area, gaining knowledge and experience and accelerating the future uptake of IP4 technologies.

Results

- The demo helped integrate traditional modes of public transport, namely GPP's trams and buses with innovative e-bike and bike-sharing services.
- The Journey Planner was found to be the best functionality, demonstrating the advantages of the synergies between bike sharing and public transport.
- Testers said that technological solutions would need further development to meet the growing demands for multimodal mobility.

Barcelona Spain

- Modes: metro, trams, buses, shared/on-demand buses
- Number of participants: 31

Testing the integration of transport-on-demand and public transport services on urban-rural connections. A focus group was also organised for a more deep and detailed testing of the solutions.

Results

- Feedback was highly positive. The focus group was successful, as the users understood the complexity of the system and the technical partners gained a better understanding of the users' needs.
- Testers reported issues and at the same time proposed improvements for the functionalities offered, contributing to inputs to enhance usability.

Warsaw Poland

- Modes: metro, trams, bus
- Number of participants: 211

The demo supported Warsaw's MaaS readiness by extending the understanding of creating MaaS schemes.

Results

- Feedback received via surveys was strongly positive, indicating that the TC application has a considerable potential.
- Participants said the app requires improvement and refinement if it is to be used on a large scale commercial basis.

Liberec-Warsaw Long-Distance Demo

- Modes: bus, train
- Number of participants: 10

Testing the multimodal cross-border connections between Liberec and Warsaw.

Results

- Testers were recruited internally, and were strongly satisfied with the IP4 Idea itself.
- The aggregation of a large number of services within a single application and thus the possibility of using a single app for travelling in Liberec, Warsaw and cross-border was particularly well-evaluated.

Conclusions

The final evaluation demonstrated the viability of the IP4MaaS solution. Overall, the feedback from users and TSPs was positive, and provided significant inputs for improvement and enhancements to the proposed services.

- Users' mobility experience proved closely linked to the availability of effective digital applications.
- To encourage consumers to change their travel habits, defining a level of convenience for the change is needed. IP4MaaS proved that the idea of integrating TSPs within a large, EU-wide network enabled by IP4 solutions could create the ideal conditions to promote this behavioural change and overcome some of the current barriers for a large-scale MaaS adoption.

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